

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Inked

– with Ink

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Corrections

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?

– Yes

Notes: As an 'alim working at Zaytuna, Ibn Ashur was employed by the government, although he was not paid specifically to write his tafsir (تفسير).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?

– I don't know

Notes: Not specifically from Ibn Ashur's interpretation of the Qur'an, but from the Qur'an itself, at least in issues related to personal status laws as these were the only ones that remained under a shari'ah scope and had not become secularized during and after the French colonization.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)...

– I don't know

Notes: Not specifically in order for Ibn Ashur to write the tafsir (تفسير), but as an 'alim (عالم) he had a special tax treatment.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Present full-time?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Present part-time?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific sex/gender?

– Yes

Notes: All male.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific ethnicity?

– No

Notes: There have been few (if any) of Imazighen origin.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific class/caste?

– Yes

Notes: Though it is not mandatory to pertain to a certain class in order to become an 'alim (عالم), it is true that lower-class people have it harder to reach the post. Also, once one becomes an 'alim, one is automatically granted great social prestige and their social status rises.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Is this class/caste based on a cultural status?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Is this class/caste based on socioeconomic status?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Are the religious specialists dedicated to the place for life?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy?

– Yes

Notes: Zaytuna 'ulama (علماء) who taught at the mosque-university usually sat around the pillars of the courtyard during lessons. Higher-ranked 'ulama chose such spaces first.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for living spaces of religious specialists?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for training spaces of religious specialists?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of a body of religious specialists?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Notes: Not in itself, but it has a considerable reputation as an interpretation.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

Notes: Classical Arabic is considered a sacred language due to the fact that the Qur'an was revealed through it. However, the text at hand combines the usage of a modernized register of Arabic to explain and comment alongside the classical Arabic in which the original texts were written.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Considered endogenous by the group itself?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Possess its own distinct written language?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ If known: which authority (authorities) describe(s) the language as sacred?

[Select all that apply]

– Institutions

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Are non-religious written languages used by the group's adherents to support religious study of text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Are oral traditions used to support the religious study of the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– I don't know

Notes: It was intended to be read by fellow 'ulama (علماء) both in Tunisia and elsewhere, but the text is sufficiently clear in its writing that it could potentially be read by other scholars of non-religious background if needed.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Notes: The text at hand is part of the Islamic reform movement (إصلاح).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Notes: There are a number of editions, but the core text is unchanged.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Qur'anic commentaries have been an important literary tradition of Islam for centuries.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Ritual list

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

– Ritual manual

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

– Index

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– Yes

Notes: However, it should be taken into consideration that at this point in time the Shari'a was largely uncodified and individual judges/ulama (علماء) relied on a plethora of sources and background knowledge to pass judgement. Among this sources lay the Qur'an, of which the text at hand is a commentary, and as such, we can say that the tafsir (تفسير) we are examining includes a legal code. However, the Qur'an is not the only source of the Shari'a and, as such, the text at hand does not reflect a complete, whole legal code, only insights and comments on the legal dispositions present in the Qur'an. It should also be noted that by the time Ibn Ashur wrote and published the text at hand, only personal status law was still being informed by the Qur'an, for the rest of the legal system had been secularized (primarily during colonial times, but it remained so after 1956, when the country regained its independence). As such, much of what is expressed by Ibn Ashur in this text does only apply to personal status laws. Although he wrote about other issues such as economic law, it hardly affected the legal system if at all.

Reference: Luz Gómez García. *Entre la sharía y la yihad : una historia intelectual del islamismo*. Madrid: Los libros de la catarata.

Reference: Wael Hallaq. *The origins and evolution of Islamic law*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Reference: Wael Hallaq B., Lawrence Conrad I.. *The formation of Islamic law*. London & New York: Routledge.

Reference: Wael Hallaq. *Authority, continuity, and change in Islamic law*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Are there formal institutions merged with the state or polity of the religious group?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Is there an institutionalized police force whose behavior is dictated by the legal code?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Is there an institutionalized judicial system whose behavior is dictated by the legal code?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Does the text in question specify institutionalized punishment?

– Yes

Notes: However, the text at hand is not the one to establish the punishments. It is the Qur'an that establishes it, the text at hand only comments on it. This tafsir could be seen as one among the many texts by Muslim reformists of the time that were trying to reshape consensus as a source for Shari'a in order to adapt Islamic legal codes to modern times, while keeping in mind the Qur'anic and traditional roots at all times.

Reference: Muhammad Zaman Qasim. *Rethinking Consensus*. (Muhammad Zaman Qasim), *Modern Islamic Thought in a Radical Age*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Execution?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Exile?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Corporal punishments?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Ostracism?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Seizure of property?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Are there any established institutionalized rewards specified in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ What is the arrangement of the calendar? [Select all that apply]

– Luni-solar? (Combined, as in Mayan, Javanese, or Cham calendars)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Does the calendar specifically dictate acceptable times for certain activities?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Planting?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Water management? (such as opening or closing dams/dykes)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Harvest?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Naming ceremonies (for toddlers)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ "First haircuts" (pre-teen)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Ceremonies marking puberty/entry into adulthood?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Marriage?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ House construction (often a metaphor for marriage)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Divorce?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Warfare?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Funerary services?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Trade/commerce?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Festivals?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s)?

– All members

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Pilgrimages?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ How strict are the stipulations regarding pilgrimage?

– obligatory for some

– obligatory for all

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Is encouraging pilgrimages a primary reason for the existence of the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Are pilgrimages guided by the text associated with particular life events?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Does pilgrimage guided by this text involve/follow major routes/roads?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Is the maintenance of the routes guided by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Is the pilgrimage conducted by walking or by other means?

– Yes

Notes: Some parts of the travel might be conducted by means other than walking, but the events taking place at the pilgrimage site itself must be conducted by walking.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Feasting?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed in accordance with the guidelines of the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that produced the text/copies of the text?

– I don't know

Notes: A part of the zakat collected each year by mosques is intended to go towards people who cannot afford feasting due to financial difficulties.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Does feasting occur in a specific locations in accordance with guidelines from the text?

– No

Notes: Although not mandatory, most of the times it is encouraged to visit the mosque to partake in the feasting alongside fellow Muslims.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Are there generally positive or negative associations with aggregates?

– Generally positive

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ If associations with mental aggregates are neither positive or negative, are there other important details to know?

– Specify: Associations can be both negative and positive, it depends on the state in question. Feeling such as anger or hatred have negative associations whereas others such as calmness have positive associations.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– Yes

Notes: There are two separate realms for the afterlife: "Jannah" (جَنَّة; lit. "garden"; often translated as Heaven), where the good ones go, and "Jahannam" (جَهَنَّمَ; often translated as Hell), where evildoers and infidels go. Both are said to exist at the same time as this world, but in different realms.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– Yes

Notes: "Jannah" (جَنَّة; lit. "garden"; often translated as Heaven) is often said to be "above", as in the sky and beyond.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– Yes

Notes: "Jahannam" (جَهَنَّمَ; often translated as Hell) is described as being below Jannah, so some sort of "below space" is present in its description.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Notes: However, it is specified that both Jannah and Jahannam coexist in time with the present world rather than being created at the end of time.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– Yes

Notes: There are a myriad of debates surrounding the terminology and its exact interpretation. For Ibn Ashur, what matters most is that there exist two separate realms, one for the believers and one for the infidels or wrongdoers, and that there is a direct relationship between people's acts in this lifetime and their reward or punishment in the afterlife.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ What are the historically mainstream positions in the debate?

– Specify: There are many debates surrounding the specifications of afterlife in Islam. For example, the number of realms that Jannah ("Heaven") has. Ibn Ashur touches upon this issue in his tafsir and goes into great detail by quoting what fellow Muslim scholars

have interpreted in the past.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

What are the historically minority positions?

– Specify: Shi'a Islam has different views on the issue.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Cremation?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Mummification?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Interment?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Cannibalism?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Feeding to animals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Secondary burial?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Re-treatment of corpse?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Are there specific designations for parts of corpses?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Could parts of corpses become transformed into partial bodily relics?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ As cenotaphs?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ In cemetery?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Other formal burial type?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

Notes: Described in anthropomorphic terms.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– I don't know

Notes: Although Allah is said to be lord of the sky and the earth and everything in between, God might be more related to the sky than to the earth, according to Ibn Ashur.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: Tunisia
- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: Tunisia
- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: Tunisia
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: Tunisia
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: Tunisia
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: Tunisia
- ↳ Other features of the supreme high god
– Specify: There are 99 names of God (الأسماء الحسنى) that describe His attributes.
Specific to this answer:
Region: Tunisia
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: God is all-knowing.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Can reward

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Can punish

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Can be hurt?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Can be tricked?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– No

Notes: In fact, as a Muslim reformer whose thought is linked to the salafiyya (السلفية) of

al-Afghani and Muhammad 'Abduh, Ibn Ashur wrote strongly against all other forms of worship or reverence, even those rooted in cultural practices such as worship of murshid.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

Notes: God communicated His will through different prophets, but can also send "signals" to people who pray, as expressed by Ibn Ashur. Despite the belief that there is no need for an intermediary between God and those who believe in Him, Ibn Ashur states that the Qur'an is a very complex text and that specific knowledge is needed in order to properly understand it, which might infer that only those with a religious education or background can properly interpret it.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ In waking, everyday life

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ In dreams

– Yes

Notes: There are instances of communication between God and some of the prophets through dreams.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ In trance possession

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Through divination practices

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Only through religious specialists

– No

Notes: However, Ibn Ashur seems to infer that commonfolk do not have the necessary knowledge to understand the Qur'an and God's intentions correctly and that only people who have undergone a religious training are 100% correct in their interpretations.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Other form of communication with living

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Notes: Ibn Ashur opposes those who believe in ghosts by insisting that all souls travel to either Jannah or Jahannam when people die, according to Qur'an, and advocates for the end of such a culturally rooted belief.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Reference: Muhammad Ibn 'Ashur al-Tahir. Surat al-Jinn. (Muhammad Ibn 'Ashur al-Tahir), Tafsīr al-taḥrīr wa al-tanwīr. Tunis: al-Dar al-Tunisiyya li-l-Nashr.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– No

Notes: Although practices such as divination by asking junun (جنون) about certain aspects of the future were present in contemporary Tunisia, Ibn Ashur advises against them and quotes numerous ayat of Surat al-Jinn (سورة الجن) to explain that God had banned them.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

Notes: Angels (ملائكة) and some junun (جنون) do.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

Notes: Some junun (جنون) do.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– Yes

Notes: Angels do not, but junun are said to behave just like human beings, hence they do eat - what they eat, however, has been up for debate for centuries as it is not explicitly stated in the Qur'an. Ibn Ashur does not touch upon this issue.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: Junun can possess people.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Are other categories of beings present?

–Other [specify]: No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Food

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Sacred space(s)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Sacred object(s)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Adultery

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Incest

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Taboo about close blood relations (beyond incest) [e.g. from same clan group, village, settlement, so forth].

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Specifies taboo regarding power relations (i.e. defines what constitutes abusive behavior)

– Yes

Notes: Between free men and slave women, for example.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Does worship/veneration include sex acts/references?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Other sexual practices

– Yes

Notes: All practices other than heterosexuality are banned.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– Yes

Notes: Particularly with regards to worshipping God.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– Yes

Notes: Technically, yes, because Islam is considered the best/only perfect religion, so it is in humanity's best interest to adhere to Islam. However, there must be no coercion to convert. Ibn Ashur states that what truths the Qur'an tells should be enough to convert others into Islam.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– Yes

Notes: Although it is only stressed in relation to worship and prayer.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Despite the fact that the most extensive and specific accounts of the Messiah are given primarily in hadith (حديث), the idea is present in the text because the Qur'an also mentions it. Ibn 'Ashur cites many ahadith in this passage, denoting the importance this source held for him. Despite not being his preferred source, he did resort to ahadith when there were doubts about the correct interpretation of the Qur'an. For example, in surat Maryam and surat Imran there is controversy over the lineage of Mary mother of Jesus and Ibn 'Ashur quoted different ahadith to clear this issue, just as he did with regards to the Messiah.

Reference: Jane Idelman Smith, Yvonne Yazbeck Haddad. *The Islamic Understanding Of Death And Resurrection*. Oxford University Press. isbn: 0195156498.

Reference: Muhammad Ibn 'Ashur. *Surat at-Takwir*. (Muhammad Ibn 'Ashur), *Tafsīr al-taḥrīr wa al-tanwīr*. Tunis: al-Dār al-Tūnisiyya li-l-Nashr.

Reference: Qais Alma'itah Salem, Zia ul Haq. *The concept of Messiah in abrahamic religions: A focused study of the eschatology of Sunni islam..* doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e09080.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Alive, identified

– Yes

Notes: There are two messianic figures said to come in the future: Jesus and Mahdi. Mahdi is a descendant of Muhammad whereas Jesus is a well-known prophet of the past who, having dwelled in Jannah for a long time, will come back near the Day of Judgement.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Coming in this lifetime

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Coming on a specified date

– Yes

Notes: Although the exact date is not given, it is known that the Messiah will come near the Day of Judgement. Mahdi will descend first and then will Jesus.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future

– I don't know

Notes: Vid. previous note.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Coming has already passed

– I don't know

Notes: It is also argued that the Prophet Muhammad played the role of a Messiah in the sense that he brought God's will and order to the Arab people and intended to restore "true religion" in the world. Regarding this, then Muhammad has already come (by the time the Qur'an was written he had already died and during revelation he had already arrived). Ibn Ashur stresses Muhammad's importance as the harbinger of Islam, although uses the term "Messiah" only to refer to Jesus.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Other purpose

– Specify: Mahdi is a messianic figure whose purpose is to guide the Muslim nation into ruling the world. Jesus' mission is to slay the Al-Masih ad-Dajjal ("False Messiah") and restore Muslim law before the Day of Judgement. Although the Al-Masih ad-Dajjal is not mentioned in the Qur'an, Ibn Ashur writes about this figure quoting various ahadith.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

Reference: Muhammad Ibn 'Ashur al-Tahir. Surat al-Haqqah. (Muhammad Ibn 'Ashur al-Tahir), Tafsīr al-taḥrīr wa al-tanwīr. Tunis: al-Dār al-Tūnisiyya li-l-Nashr.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ At specified time in future

– Yes

Notes: The exact date isn't given, but it is called the Day of Judgment.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ At unspecified time in near future

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ At some other time [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Divine judgment event

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Restoration of the world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Establishment of new political system

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Establishment of new religious system

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?

– I don't know

Notes: If we understand the term "survive" to mean "keep alive in the same form as before", then no, because humanity and all of God's creation will undergo major transformations and will either end up either in Jannah or in Jahannam. However, in the sense that no one will be left behind in this transformation, then every person who has ever lived will "survive" the eschaton.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Yes

Notes: The book at hand is not a fiqh (فقه) treatise, but it does delve somewhat deep into aspects such as the necessary differentiation between mutable (mu`āmalāt (معاملات)) and immutable (`aqīda (عقيدة) and `ibāda (عبادة)) dispositions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ What is the nature of this distinction?

– Present & clear

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being

– Yes

Notes: They are direct commands of God (who is described in anthropomorphic terms).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no (sic: have no?) special connection to the metaphysical

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Moral norms apply to (select all that apply)

– All individuals (any time period)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Courage (in battle)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Courage (generic)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Yes

Notes: Much could be said about this topic, but, in summary, despite doing a considerable effort to modernize the concept of family in his tafsir (تفسير), Ibn Ashur still upheld traditional values such as filial piety, obedience to husbands from wives, etc.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Cooperation

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Moderation/frugality

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Power/status/nobility

– No

Notes: Despite their social importance, these qualities were not given religious importance by Ibn Ashur, hence he did not write much about them in his tafsir.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Humility/modesty

– Yes

Notes: It is emphasized more towards women and people who have been assigned female at birth. However, Ibn Ashur wrote against the veil insisting that it was a social custom that did not have religious roots.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Optimism/hope

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– Yes

Notes: It is emphasized with regards to religious rituals in which cleanliness is a must and Ibn Ashur tries to advise people to be clean and keep order in their houses.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Monogamy (males)

– No

Notes: However, the Qur'anic verses relating to polygyny are polemic. During Ibn Ashur's time, the debate centered around the idea of whether Qur'an IV:129 abrogated IV:3 or not. Ibn Ashur stated that the measure was put into practice in order to avoid fornication and related crimes, and that the limitation of 4 women per man was established to ensure that no women was left alone (since he believed that there were more women than men due to wars killing the latter and the longer lifespans attributed to the former). Ibn Ashur does believe that polygyny should be a last resort, only in times of need, and should not serve as an excuse to satisfy the lower desires of men. However, he does not understand Qur'an IV:129 as having abrogated IV:3, therefore deems the number of 4 wives correct.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Monogamy (females)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Other sexual constraints (males)

– Yes

Notes: Sexual orientations other than heterosexuality are banned.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Other sexual constraints (females)

– Yes

Notes: Sexual orientations other than heterosexuality are banned.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Does the text require castration?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Notes: The text talks about the marginalization that Muslim communities used to suffer when Islam was first expanding as well as about those faced by diasporic communities in European countries of Christian majority, but it does not 'require' marginalization.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

What is the average interval of time between performances?

– I don't know

Notes: Five times a day, but since prayer times are regulated by daily astronomical phenomena, they are not fixed.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– I don't know

Notes: As many as possible.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– I don't know

Notes: Vid. note about prayer times.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Are there orthodoxy checks?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– Yes

Notes: They mostly involve women's outfit checks, confirmation that no participant is under the influence of either alcohol nor drugs and/or confirmation that ritual purification has taken place.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– Yes

Notes: During prayer, movements are supposed to be synchronic between all participants. The same is true during pilgrimage rituals.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Notes: Ibn Ashur censors this practice, common between members of the same Suffi order.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

Notes: The sacrifice of lambs during Eid al-Adha (عيد الأضحى), for example.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ By the community?

– Yes

Notes: However, there are exceptions: people who are sick or too old, assigned-female-at-birth people who are menstruating and young children are exempt from participating in fasting.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ By specific individuals?

– Yes

Notes: Men and assigned-male-at-birth people are required to assist the mosque for praying, whereas their female counterparts are exempt from the obligation.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– I don't know

Notes: Ibn Ashur's tafsir does not, in itself, regulate the maintenance of mosques or other sacred places. However, in discussing the Qur'anic dispositions surrounding such issues, the book touches on the topic. All of Ibn Ashur's comments are in line with hegemonic beliefs of his time.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A state

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: The 'ulama (علماء) of al-Zaytuna, from whom came all interpretations of Qur'an before, did influence Ibn Ashur's thought. Although he considered himself amongst the reformist group (and

certainly was), some conservative ideas still permeated his thought and are present throughout the text at hand. Although he used more modern terminology to describe the family and its roles, gendered roles are still traditionally rooted and the shift is not from a conservative to a more reformist mentality, but from a "traditional" to a "modern" justification of almost the same mentality as before.

Reference: Hitomi Ono. The Concept of the Family and Gender Norms: The Works of Tunisian Islamic Scholar Ibn 'Āshūr.

Reference: Hitomi Ono. The Family in the Thought of Ibn 'Āshūr: Islamic Traditions and Modern Patriarchy.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– Yes

Notes: For example, when distributing the lamb slaughtered during Eid al-Adha it is written that a part of such meal must go to those who suffer from hunger, who are poor and cannot partake in the celebrations, etc.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– Yes

Notes: When referencing the zaka, it is written that a part of such money must go to those who suffer from hunger, who are poor and in need, etc.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– I don't know

Notes: The text itself does not delve too deeply into this issue, but it does infer that women should take care of the elderly as well as of children in their household.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Notes: However, Ibn Ashur does talk about the need for institutions such as kuttab (Qur'anic schools) and higher education ones such as the Zaytuna mosque and praises its role in teaching Qur'anic studies.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– I don't know

Notes: The text is very centered in religious education as Ibn Ashur understands that all education could potentially be religious given the fact that the Qur'an and ahadith insist in the need for every Muslim person to seek out knowledge. All source of knowledge is God and His creation, hence all knowledge has a religious component in it. However, Ibn Ashur did advocate for an educational reform, including modern sciences and foreign languages, which were not considered to be "religious" except by virtue of this train of thought.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Notes: Ibn Ashur makes no distinction between education for males/men and females/women,

claiming that all Muslims should have access to education. However, certain subjects remain in the realm of either men or women, such as warfare for the former and childrearing for the latter.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: Teachers should be respected, but it is true that the text is not so strict when it comes to showing disagreement with teachers. Ibn Ashur, although not openly, suggests that when done with respect and humility, disagreeing with a teacher is not something bad but can, in fact, help both student and teacher to grow and become more knowledgeable.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– Yes

Notes: Primarily, access to better jobs and salaries, but also contributing to the betterment of life for the country and its people. There are also other "religious" rewards as Ibn Ashur believes that by knowing more about nature and God's creation, people get to know and love God even more.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy permanently?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy temporarily/seasonally?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Does the text dictate how the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Does the text dictate how individuals interact with other institutional bureaucracies?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Does the text regulate the primary supporting income of the place?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out land?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out tools?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Does the text advocate for public food storage?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Does the text provide guidance for food distribution?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Does the text regulate places for civic functions?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Does the text regulate places for the practice of justice?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Does the text advocate or specify controls for water management (irrigation, flood control)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Does the text specify restrictions on common transportation?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Does the text require the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– Yes

Notes: The government.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Is taxation linked to an understanding of charitable giving?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– Yes

Notes: Ibn Ashur insists that Muslim people should only fight to protect others, the Umma (Islamic nation) or their respective homelands.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– I don't know

Notes: Though Ibn Ashur was a nationalist at heart, not much of it can be inferred through his tafsir.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Does the text in question dictate how the religious group in question provide food for themselves?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Does the text celebrate/restrict food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– No

Notes: So long as the food is Halal, it is approved for consumption, regardless of who procured it.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

↳ Which of the follow are forms of ritual food production [choose all that apply]?

– Gathering

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

– Hunting (including marine animals)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

– Fishing

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

– Pastoralism

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

– Small-scale agriculture/horticultural gardens or orchards

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

– Large-scale agriculture (E.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Tunisia

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